

EFFECTS OF PEER TUTORING USING BLAAN-TRANSLATED WORD PROBLEMS TOWARDS THE PERFORMANCE IN MATHEMATICS OF GRADE 7 BLAAN LEARNERS

Jovy Lane Garcia Sebu, LPT, MAED¹, Sherwin Pullan Uy, LPT, Ed.D.²

¹ *Lampitak National High School, Tampakan, South Cotabato, Philippines*

² *Part-Time Professor, Graduate School, Holy Trinity College of General Santos City, General Santos City, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14253023>

ABSTRACT

This study determined the effects of peer tutoring using Blaan-translated word problems towards the performance in mathematics of the Grade 7 Blaan learners of Lampitak National High School. There were sixty (60) Grade 7 Blaan learners and they were divided into two groups: the control group, which was taught on how to solve English-worded problems in Mathematics using traditional lecture method; and the experimental group which was taught by applying peer-to-peer learning strategy as an intervention during the class session. The data had been analyzed at 0.05 level of significance using the frequency count, mean, percentage, and t-tests for independent and dependent samples. The t-test results with the mean difference of 6.67, $t\text{-value} = -5.073$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.000$ between the pretest and post-test among the experimental group showed that the performance of Grade 7 Blaan learners in solving English-worded problems in mathematics is affected by peer tutoring using Blaan-translated word problems. The result revealed that there is a poor level of knowledge among the two groups at the start of the study. It further emphasized that employing peer-tutoring using the Blaan language is effective in improving the performance of Blaan learners in Mathematics than teaching using the traditional method without peer tutoring.

Keywords: *peer tutoring, Blaan-translated word problems, English-worded problems, Lampitak National High School)*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching mathematics aims to enhance the knowledge of the learners through learning by doing and discovering potentials by testing their computational skills using worded problems based on the competency in the learning curriculum guide. However, in today's Philippine education set up, especially in the remote areas where learners come from the indigenous group, Mathematics teachers experience difficulties in imparting lessons and in developing solving skills in mathematics. In this study, the learners come from the barangays wherein, most of the community members are Blaan. These Blaan learners need to enhance their comprehension ability with various strategies in order to realize the value of computation as applied to real life problems. This group of learners reside in Barangay Lampitak, Municipality of Tampakan, where the Lampitak National High School is situated.

The Lampitak National High School finds problems with the mathematical skills of the Blaan learners considering that it is an Indigenous People school. As observed, the Grade 7 learners, especially the Blaan learners, were very slow in solving word problems in mathematics. The basic concept in mathematics is not mastered and this gives difficulties to the teachers. It is hard for them to manage the different learning styles of Blaan learners. As observed, most of them are passive and lack interest in learning, specifically in solving problems that need literacy and numeracy skills. It is also noticed that most of the Grade 7 Blaan learners lack self-confidence in expressing their ideas or even in asking questions regarding the lesson. Teachers have tried to apply differentiated instruction during the teaching-learning process but problems on developing their skills on how to solve English-worded problems in mathematics still need to be enhanced.

As a mathematics teacher who is not a Blaan, it is really a struggle to address the needs of the Blaan learners in developing their skills on how to solve English-worded mathematical problems. As experienced, it is difficult to deepen the important concepts if teachers do not use the learners' language.

Hence, taking into consideration the Blaan learners' needs, to contextualize the lesson in mathematics through a learning strategy which is based on their ability and skills in solving problems such as a proposed intervention of Peer Tutoring using Blaan language. This may help them improve their solving skills and may urge them to improve their mathematical ability and discover the bright side of learning how to comprehend and solve English-worded problems.

It is through mathematics where everyone can develop their critical thinking not only about numbers, equations, and computations, but also in comprehension where the ability of the learners to think logically may increase. According to McKellar (2006), the most beautiful thing in mathematics is not typically the application but the art form that it illustrates. It is an art where anyone could create special techniques and strategies in solving problems towards the desirable solution. The application of mathematics in everyday living is essential to every individual, especially the skills to be developed in solving English-worded problems. As stated by Eviriyanti, et al. (2017), mathematics is

one of the subjects that occupy a significant role in education. It is one way of teaching the learners how to use their knowledge logically and in a systematic way towards solving problems.

Problem solving, as utilized in mathematics learning literature, refers to the process wherein the learners encounter a problem—a question that needs a mathematical solution. In this sense, learners should read and comprehend the problem in order to find a correct process to arrive at the correct answer.

Moreover, Apino and Retnawati (2016) explained that everyone should have a variety of 21st century skills comprising creativity, reasoning, and problem solving in this modern era. It is therefore learning in a creative way that learners could acquire knowledge and develop various skills including working collaboratively with their peers and engaging learners to analyze real life experiences that may help in developing problem solving skills.

Meanwhile, in the context of peer-assisted learning, peer tutoring may help in developing both academic and non-academic skills among learners inside the classroom wherein learners in a class are paired to think and share their ideas in acquiring knowledge. Persuasion of peers in the attainment of learners' education is the ultimate aim by educators, parents, and researchers. Peer effects may transpire through finding common interests and willingness to share knowledge with proficiency in assisting their peers to mutually develop learning. Classroom decisions about the learners grouping, whether through formal chasing or informal activities, are guided by principles about how learners cooperate and learn from each other (Kim, 2016). In solving word problems, peer tutoring may help a lot to improve learners' performance.

In the Philippine education curriculum, problem solving has been incorporated as part of competency that every Filipino learner should learn. Yet, difficulty in attaining the goals of the Department of Education (DepEd) was met by some mathematics teachers today especially those who were designated at the rural areas. Albona (2015) cited that learners of the Indigenous People, specifically the Blaan learners, experienced difficulty in comprehending academic subjects that are taught in school. This results in them having failing grades or even dropping from school. As observed, there were learners who are very poor in problem solving especially in answering worded-problems. Being a mathematics teacher who is not a Blaan and does not know how to speak the Blaan language, it is hard to impart knowledge specifically to elucidate the process of solving English-worded problems in mathematics because Blaan learners easily understand the discussions if Blaan language was used. This scenario arouses the interest of the researcher in order to help the Blaan learners; to assist them increase their performance, gain appropriate and creative techniques and develop confidence in solving mathematical-worded problems. Hence, peer tutoring was proposed as a learning intervention among the Blaan learners.

Indeed, peer-to-peer tutoring is a common intervention in classroom settings. This study gives value not only to highlight peer tutoring as a learning strategy but also to help

address the needs of Blaan learners in their difficulty in learning mathematics. This study may inspire them to enrich their interest in learning mathematics because with their peers, they could freely ask questions and express their difficulties in learning the subject.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effects of peer tutoring using Blaan-translated word problems towards the performance in mathematics of the Grade 7 Blaan learners. This was conducted at Lampitak National High School for the academic year 2019-2020.

Specifically, the researcher answered the following questions:

1. What is the result of the pretest on a traditional lecture method using English-worded problems in mathematics among the control group of Grade 7 Blaan learners?
2. What is the result of the pretest on a peer tutoring method using English-worded problems in mathematics among the experimental group of Grade 7 Blaan learners?
3. Is there a significant difference in the result of pretest scores between the control group and experimental group of Grade 7 Blaan learners?
4. What is the result of the post-test on a traditional lecture method using English-worded problems in mathematics among the control group of Grade 7 Blaan learners?
5. What is the result of the post-test on peer tutoring method using English-worded problems in mathematics among the experimental group of Grade 7 Blaan learners?
6. Is there a significant difference in the result of the post-test between the control group and experimental group?
7. Is there a significant difference between the results of pretest and post-test among the control group?
8. Is there a significant difference between the results of pretest and post-test among the experimental group?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

This study was conducted in Lampitak National School located at Sitio Melina, Barangay Lampitak, Tampakan, South Cotabato. It is about nine kilometers away from the town proper. Lampitak is one of the barangays in Tampakan with a bigger number of ethnic groups residing in this barangay. Among the ethnic groups in the Municipality of Tampakan, Blaan is one of the biggest groups whose indigenous communities have been overrun by lowland settlers. These migrations have resulted in multilingual cultural setting. In Lampitak National High School, the majority of the learners are Blaan. This school was founded in 2004. It was during this year that through the initiatives of the barangay council, the Barangay Resolution Number 40 series of 2004 requesting the Department of Education to establish Secondary School in Barangay Lampitak was approved. It was on March 15, 2004 that ushered brighter hopes for the constituents of

Lampitak and nearby barangays. Though establishing a school is a big responsibility, the service oriented and dedicated public servants extended their heartfelt support that results in the continuous improvement of the school. The school starts to operate with 123 enrollees and 5 teachers. As observed, every year, the school is increasing its number of enrollees.

During the School Year 2019-2020, the school was composed of 15 teachers and one school head. Based on the official record on the Learner Information System, the school had 404 enrollees comprising of 232 IP learners. There were 336 junior high school learners and 68 were officially enrolled as senior high school learners. Specifically, the subjects of this study were the 60 Grade 7 Blaan learners.

Subjects of the Study

The identified subjects of this study were the 60 Grade 7 Blaan learners of Lampitak National High School. The researcher used a Restricted Random Sampling technique based on the officially enrolled Grade 7 Blaan learners listed in LIS generated School Form 1 for School Year 2019-2020. The control and experimental groups of Grade 7 Blaan learners were selected fairly by means of draw lots done by the class adviser.

The Experimental Group. The experimental group of 30 Grade 7 Blaan learners came from a heterogeneous class of 48 officially enrolled learners including the non-Blaan learners. To determine who among the learners were in the experimental group, drawing of lots was made by the class adviser and restricted the selection to the Blaan learners only. The conduct of the experiment was done during the regular time schedule of the researcher as their mathematics teacher. Before the experiment was conducted, a 30-item pretest was administered. The Pretest was composed of English-worded problems in mathematics on sets, integers, rational numbers and real numbers which was administered in one hour. The number of word problems in each topic was based on the Table of Specification (TOS) made by the researcher. Questions are aligned with the problems in the learner's module that was based on the learning competency found in the Grade 7 Mathematics Curriculum Guide set by the DepEd.

During the conduct of the study, the researcher, as mathematics teacher, taught every lesson by means of lecture method but deepened the concept and conducted the activity through peer tutoring. The advanced knowledgeable Blaan learners were paired to slow Blaan learners to apply a peer-to-peer learning using the Blaan language in their discussion. The Blaan-translated word problem exercises prepared by the researcher were also used during the peer tutoring. Post-test was administered after all topics had been discussed.

The Control Group. There were 30 Grade 7 Blaan learners who served as the control group from another heterogeneous section of 49 officially enrolled Grade 7 learners. A simple random sampling through drawing of lots was made by their class adviser in order to identify the 30 respondents for the control group of this research. The control group also answered a 30-item pretest with the same content of the pretest given to the

experimental group of learners. During the conduct of the study, a traditional lecture method using materials in teaching such as chalk and chalkboard was used during the discussion. The activities and exercises given to this group were based on the Learners' Module; the learners answer the activity without the intervention of peer tutoring. After the discussions of all the topics, a post-test has been administered.

Moreover, the non-Blaan Grade 7 learners were also involved in class discussions and activities. Nevertheless, their output was gathered as part of the class but not for the purpose of being a subject of the study. Therefore, in both experimental group and control group, data from the non-Blaan learners were not included in the data analysis.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher ensured that all ethical considerations were followed as mandated by the Holy Trinity College Ethical Review Board because it helped to avoid engaging in practices which may implicitly or explicitly abuse or exploit those whom she sought to do research with.

In addition, to evade any undesirable discernment and to safeguard the personal information that may lead to bounded details through answering the research questions, the respondents were assured that the researcher would preserve their responses with utmost ethical contemplations. This study was guided by the ethical principles of Mack et al. (2005), which are: respect for persons, kindness, integrity, permission, and privacy.

Respect for persons involves assurance of the authority of the respondents to preserve their personality and to not divulge their weaknesses (Sargeant, 2012). Before the conduct of the study, consent was secured from the Schools Division Superintendents and to the school head of Lampitak National High School. On the other hand, kindness entails commitment to increase the welfare and reduce the possibilities that the research may be associated with emotional and societal risks of the respondents. With utmost kindheartedness, data gathered from the respondents was kept to avoid dispersing of information.

Another ethical principle is integrity. This guarantees a just dissemination of the research results; neither it could harm or benefit others. Efforts should be acknowledged even from the formulation of plans until the gathering of data, and to all procedures wherein the respondents contribute to the success of the conduct of study. Symbolic gratitude should also be given to the respondents because it is through them and their effort that lead the positive upgrading of the teachers' strategies in teaching and helping the researcher's career development (Tiburcio et al., 2018).

Lastly, permission and privacy is an ethical principle that ensures that respondents understand their involvement in the study-its usefulness and contributions in the field of education. Their vital role, however, must show their willingness in participating in the conduct of the research process. However, the researcher must reveal the assurance of the results and secure the confidentiality of the respondents' personal information and answers to the questions (Tiburcio et al., 2018).

To avoid unfavorable results and maintain fastidiousness in the study, the researcher shows an energetic understanding of the different involvements hiding the personal information of the respondents. This quantitative study inspires the researcher to value the importance of improving the ability of Blaán learners in solving mathematical-worded problems. This could help Blaán learners to develop their performance on the least learned competency in Grade 7 to enhance their mathematical problem solving skills.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before the conduct of the study, the researcher sent letters addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent of South Cotabato Division, to the School Head of Lampitak National High School, and to the Indigenous Peoples Mandatory Representative of the Municipal Cultural Affairs of Tampakan Municipality, asking permission to conduct a study in the concerned school. The researcher conducted the study within four weeks during the month of January 2020.

A questionnaire for pretest that was designed by the researcher was used in the conduct of the study. It was validated and gained a mean of 4.7 which specifies that the questionnaire is highly valid to measure the variables in the study. The pre-test on English-worded mathematical problems was employed to both experimental group and control group before the experiment was conducted.

In imparting the identified subject matter to the learners during the experiment, two types of Learning Plan were used. For the experimental group, the learning plan consists of Blaán-translated activity/learning exercises on mathematical word problems which was utilized during the peer tutoring activity. Learners with advanced knowledge in mathematics, specifically in finding solutions on English-worded problems, served as tutors and those who had difficulties in understanding and solving word problems in mathematics were the tutees. The tutors used different learning strategies in dealing with their tutees in such a way that their peers could easily understand the problem. The tutors were assigned randomly in every session to experience and apply different schemes during peer tutoring and to fairly assess each tutee's performance. The learning development of the Blaán learners through peer tutoring using their own language surpassed the challenges met by each learner in solving English-worded problems in mathematics.

In the control group however, it followed the Learning Plan which utilized the traditional lecture method wherein peer tutoring is not applied. After the experiment, a post-test was administered to both experimental and control groups of the Grade 7 Blaán learners. The results of the pretest and post-test were properly recorded and computed to complete the information for the data analysis.

Research Instrument

In the conduct of this study, the tools used were the learning plan for the experimental group, Learning Plan for the Control Group, the Table of Specification

(TOS), a researcher-made test on English-worded problems in mathematics which was utilized during the pretest and post-test, and a compilation of Blaan-translated word problem exercises based on the Learning Module utilized during the peer tutoring activity that was incorporated to the learning plan for the experimental group.

Learning Plan for the Experimental Group. The researcher prepared a semi-detailed learning plan for the experimental group. This is shown in Appendix F. The learning plan consists of the topics taught in a specific range of time during the conduct of the study. It consists of the achievable objectives, content standards, performance standards, learning competencies, the subject matter, and the procedure of the learning process. This learning plan is composed of activities that use peer-to-peer learning as an intervention to assist Blaan learners in the schoolroom activities. The tutor uses Blaan language to deepen the mathematical concept to their tutee and uses the Blaan-translated word problems given in each topic as exercises. This learning plan was prepared based on the regular class schedule for the experimental group of Grade 7 learners.

Learning Plan for the Control Group. This can be shown in Appendix G. The learning plan consists of topics taught in a specific length of time; this serves as a guide of the researcher in the conduct of the study. It is a semi-detailed learning plan that consists of the achievable objectives, content standards, performance standards, learning competencies, the subject matter, and the procedure of the learning process. However, in this plan, peer tutoring has not been applied during the conduct of the study. It follows the traditional method of instruction to the control group of Grade 7 learners without peer tutoring in various activities and exercises in every lesson.

Table of Specification (TOS). In this study, the Table of Specification was shown in Appendix E. This was used as the basis for an accurate distribution of the test items in the pretest and post-test. This was created based on the Grade 7 learning competencies and it points out how the test items were constructed according to Bloom's Taxonomy Level of Learning that contained Remembering, Understanding, Applying, Analyzing, Evaluating and Creating. The TOS was constructed based on the prepared learning plan of the researcher for the conduct of this study.

Pretest and Post-test. These are researcher-made tests which utilize the Table of Specification as a guide. It was shown in Appendix D. The pretest and post-test were composed of thirty (30) multiple choice items on English-worded problems in mathematics with the following topics: sets, integers, rational numbers, and real numbers. The test questionnaire is distributed into Remembering 30%, Understanding 20%, Applying 20%, Analyzing 10%, Evaluating 10% and Creating 10%. These tests were administered to both control and experimental group of Grade 7 learners.

The questionnaire was validated by teacher-experts who have adequate knowledge in mathematics. They are all Master Teachers and have been teaching mathematics for more than 10 years. Using the school's standard validator's questionnaires assessment tool, the evaluators gained an overall mean of 4.7 which indicates that the questionnaire is highly valid to measure the variables in the study.

The following scale was used to describe the scores of learners based on the indicated interval:

Score Range	Description	Interpretation
25-30	Very Good	The learners have a very high level of computational skills in mathematical word problems.
19-24	Good	The learners have a high level of computational skills in mathematical word problems.
13-18	Fair	The learners have a moderate level of computational skills in mathematical word problems.
7-12	Poor	The learners have a poor level of computational skills in mathematical word problems.
0-6	Very Poor	The learners have a very poor level of comprehension in solving word problems in mathematics.

Moreover, the Blaan-translated word problems exercises incorporated in the Learning Plan for Experimental Group were validated by the Blaan mathematics teachers. In validating the questionnaire, the standard validation tool for quantitative study provided by the Holy Trinity College Graduate School was utilized. With the overall mean of 3.5, it revealed that the compiled Blaan-translated word problems exercises that were incorporated in the learning plan for experimental group are valid and can be utilized in the conduct of the study.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were employed and tested using 0.05 level of significance in the study.

To determine the result of the pretest on English-worded problems in mathematics among the control and experimental group of Grade 7 Blaan learners, frequency count and mean were used. However, to determine the significant difference in the result of the pretest between the control group and experimental group of Grade 7 Blaan learners, t-test for independent samples was utilized. Furthermore, to determine the result of the post-test among the control and experimental groups of Grade 7 Blaan learners, frequency count and mean were used.

To determine the significant difference between the result of Pretest and post-test among the control group, t-test for dependent samples was employed.

Lastly, to determine the significant difference between the result of pretest and post-test among the experimental group, t-test for dependent samples was utilized.

For the analysis of data, the study includes the summary of the quantity of data collected and presented the results by way of discussing the vital features of the study (Tiburcio et al., 2018).

After the conduct of the experiment, the post-test was employed. Only the data of the specified subjects of the study were tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted. The data used is the pretest and post-test results of both control and experimental groups. In tabulating the data, statistical information was verified through the results based on the test materials used. Analyzing the data however, bridged the conclusion to revisit the results of the data. In making the interpretation of the study, valid data were the basis in order that the interpretation of the data is clear, exact, factual, and based on the personal analysis of the subjects.

Scope and Limitations

This study focuses on determining the effects of peer tutoring using Blaan-translated word problems towards the performance in mathematics of the Grade 7 Blaan learners. Peer tutoring in this study is a peer-to-peer student learning strategy that serves as an intervention to assist other learners in their difficulties in solving English-worded problems in mathematics. This peer tutoring was conducted during the regular classes which found out to be an effective interference to the Blaan learners that helped improve their performance in mathematics.

This study was conducted in Lampitak National School, one of the Secondary Schools in District II Tampakan. The subjects were the Grade 7 Blaan learners who are officially enrolled for the school year 2019-2020. The subjects of this study were divided into two groups: the control group which consists of 30 Grade 7 Blaan learners and taught how to solve English-worded problems through traditional lecture method; and, the experimental group which consists of 30 Grade 7 Blaan learners who were taught applying peer tutoring method as an intervention during the class session. The coverage of this study was based on the learning competencies stipulated in the Curriculum Guide of Grade 7 Mathematics and was conducted during the third quarter for the School Year 2019-2020.

However, during the conduct of the study, some difficulties were encountered that affect the findings of the data gathered such as lack of mastery on the basic concept in mathematics that shows poor performance of the learners as seventh graders which also brought difficulties in time management of the researcher on how to meet the target objectives based on the allotted time for a specific activity since basic concept is not mastered. Another problem is the learning style that includes learners' attitude of not frequently going to school as affected by their family's economic instability. With this, the pairing of learners during the peer tutoring activity was affected and the researcher found a problem in accumulating the activity and test results due to the learners' absences.

Another is the difficulty in finding and applying strategies that could minimize learners' attitude of being passive in learning mathematics.

In addition, the teacher-researcher also met complications on the influence of some unnecessary information from social media because this develops passivism towards learning. The diversion of learners' attention to their gadgets by prioritizing non-educational information instead of the lesson is one of the problems that challenged the researcher. To teach the Blaan learners, it needs more motivation in order for the learners to prioritize learning in education and shun non-educational social media interaction.

Lastly, a problem of being a non-Blaan teacher who is not knowledgeable in the Blaan language was met. During the peer tutoring activity, it is hard to assist the tutors in explaining the concept to the tutees using their own language. There was also difficulty in evaluating the tutor's discussion if the explanation followed the correct process in solving problems. Hence, the result of tutees' performance measures the mastery of tutor's deliberation of the concepts during the peer tutoring using the Blaan language.

RESULTS

Pretest Result on Traditional Lecture Method using English-worded Problems in Mathematics Among the Control Group of Grade 7 Blaan Learners

This study attempted to determine the level of performance in solving English-worded problems in mathematics among the control group of Grade 7 Blaan learners. To do this, a 30-item pretest was given to the learners and the results were analyzed. Table 1 shows the results.

Table 1

Pretest Result on Traditional Lecture Method using English-worded Problems in Mathematics Among the Control Group of Grade 7 Blaan Learners

Range of Test Scores	f	%	Description
25 – 30	0	0%	Very Good
19 – 24	0	0%	Good
13 – 18	6	20.00%	Fair
7 – 12	22	73.30%	Poor
0 – 6	2	6.70%	Very Poor

Overall Mean Score	9.80	Poor
---------------------------	-------------	-------------

The result on Table 1 shows that 73.30% of the control group got scores of 7 to 12 during the pretest. This score is based on the perfect score of 30, hence, this performance is considered Poor. This is followed by the 20% who got scores of 13-18 which is considered as a Fair performance. However, there were only 6.70% of the learners who scored 0-6 which is considered as a Very Poor performance.

The mean score of the control group during the pretest on English-worded Problems in mathematics is only 9.80 which indicates that the learners perform poorly in solving English-worded problems. This result explains that the culture-based learning for Blaans learners is much needed. Most of the parents of these indigenous learners are uneducated and could not give sufficient support in their children's studies. Low achievers depend on the assistance to be given to them by the people that surround them at home and in school. This scenario perhaps makes Blaans learners unable to gain enough knowledge in school. Their foundation in computational skills and comprehension in English-worded problems is not strong because they needed cultural adjustment in order to learn better in numbers and in learning mathematical language.

Moreover, most of the Grade 7 Blaans learners who showed poor performance at the start of the study implies that their basic knowledge in mathematics is far behind the cognitive level they should possess (Bosman & Schulze, 2018).

Pretest Result on Peer Tutoring Method using English-worded Problems in Mathematics Among the Experimental Group of Grade 7 Blaans Learners

In determining the level of performance in solving English-worded problems in mathematics of the Grade 7 Blaans learners among the experimental group, a 30-item pretest was given to the learners and the results were analyzed. Table 2 shows the results.

Table 2

Pretest Result on Peer Tutoring Method using English-worded Problems in Mathematics Among the Experimental Group of Grade 7 Blaans Learners

Range of Test Scores	f	%	Description
25 – 30	1	3.30%	Very Good
19 – 24	1	3.30%	Good
13 – 18	9	30.00%	Fair
7 – 12	11	36.70%	Poor
0 – 6	8	26.70%	Very Poor

Overall Mean Scores	9.93	Poor
----------------------------	-------------	-------------

The result on Table 2 revealed that 36.70% among the experimental group got scores of 7 to 12 during the pretest on English-worded problems in mathematics which is based on a perfect score of thirty (30); this performance is considered Poor. This is followed by the 30% who got scores of 13-18, which is considered a Fair performance. There were 26.70% learners who got scores of 0-6 which is considered as Very Poor. Only 3.30% of the learners got scores of 25-30 which is considered as Good and the same percentage also got a Very Good performance.

The mean score of the pretest result among the experimental group on English-worded problems in mathematics is only 9.93 which signifies that the learners perform poorly in solving English-worded problems.

The result implies that there is a lack of numeracy skills among the Grade 7 Blaan learners. Their computational skills and ability to comprehend English-worded problems in mathematics is inappropriate to their level as 7th Grader that was possibly caused by home environment considering that it is the first school wherein learners' education depends on family background and economic status, which plays an important role in studying mathematics. In addition, the poor performance at the beginning of the study signifies that the learners' prior knowledge of the basic concepts in mathematics is not fully mastered.

Hence, learners need to strengthen the basic concepts in mathematics in order to improve their performance in comprehending and solving mathematical word problems. Strong foundation on basic concepts in mathematics is very crucial for all learners for it is the reference point as they continue learning. Without enough knowledge on the basic concepts in mathematics, this leads the learners to deal with more difficult tasks in finding solutions to problems such as identifying the process, the formulas, and the correct interpretation just to arrive at the correct solution to the given problem (Retnawati et al., 2017).

Significant Difference on the Result of Pretest Scores Between the Control Group and Experimental Group of Grade 7 Blaan Learners

This study evaluated whether there is a significant difference on the result of the pretest scores between the control group and experimental group of learners. To do this, t-test for independent samples was used. Table 3 shows the result.

Table 3

Significant Difference on the Result of Pretest Scores Between the Control Group and Experimental Group of Grade 7 Blaan Learners

Groups	Mean	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Control	9.80	0.126	0.900	No Significant Difference
Experimental	9.93			
Mean Difference	0.13			

In the 30-item test on English-worded problems in mathematics, the control group of learners got a mean score of 9.80 while the experimental group of learners got a mean score of 9.93. This yields t-value of 0.126 and a p-value of 0.900. Since $p > 0.05$, then there is No Significant Difference in the mean score between the control group and experimental group of the Grade 7 Blaan learners in solving English-worded problems in mathematics. This means that the control group and experimental group of Blaan learners perform equally in solving English-worded problems in mathematics during the conduct of pretest. This result therefore, failed to reject the null hypothesis that there is No Significant Difference in the pretest scores between the control group and experimental group of Grade 7 Blaan learners. This group of Blaan learners shows a problem with language and lack of prerequisite knowledge in basic computational skills in mathematics because of cultural difficulties and family's socio-economic status. The inadequate food at home and lack of support system from the family make learners struggle in learning.

Hence, both the control and experimental groups found difficulties in answering the given English-worded problems in mathematics. Their ability to comprehend and analyze mathematical ideas and techniques are poor (Mazana et al., 2019). Furthermore, the result revealed that the poor performance of learners in mathematics is affected by some factors including learners' attitude that refers to their interest in learning the subject, the instructional technique used by teachers that could not motivate learners to actively participate in class discussions, the school environment that is not conducive for learning, and the family that daily influence them at home (Retnawati et al., 2017).

Post-test Result on the Traditional Lecture Method using English-worded Problems in Mathematics Among the Control Group of Grade 7 Blaan Learners

This study also determined the result of the post-test on English-worded mathematical word problems among the control group of Grade 7 Blaan learners. A 30-

item post-test was given to the learners and the results were analyzed. Table 4 shows the result.

Table 4

Post-test Result on the Traditional Lecture Method using English-worded Problems in Mathematics Among the Control Group of Grade 7 Blaan Learners

Range of Test Scores	f	%	Description
25 – 30	0	0%	Very Good
19 – 24	2	6.70%	Good
13 – 18	7	23.30%	Fair
7 – 12	18	60.00%	Poor
0 – 6	3	10.00%	Very Poor
Overall Mean Score		10.77	Poor

As shown in Table 4, it emphasized that the majority or 60% of the learners got scores of 7 to 12. This is based on the perfect score of thirty (30). This performance is considered Poor. This is followed by the 23.30% who got scores of 13-18 which is considered as a Fair performance. There were 10% of the learners who got scores of 0-6 which is considered as a Very Poor Performance. And only 6.70% with scores of 19-24 are considered having a Good Performance. The overall mean score among the control group in solving English-worded mathematical word problems is only 10.77 which signifies that learners still perform poorly in solving English-worded problems.

This result implied that teaching Blaan learners employing traditional methods is not enough to help them comprehend mathematical concepts and apply those concepts to the lesson discussion.

According to Simamora et al. (2017), in applying traditional methods in teaching, few students are able to grasp quickly during the lesson discussion. The quality of teaching-learning process in the classroom is much dependent on what the teachers could do towards the learners. The teaching style of the teacher may be mismatched with the learning and teaching style of the learners (Zakaria & Syamaun, 2017). It means that the teachers' teaching strategy did not fit the learners' learning preferences and styles. Learners are seeking teaching approaches that satisfy them to easily comprehend the lesson during the discussion.

Moreover, from the researcher's point of view, learners' understanding towards the lesson depends on how the teacher discusses and delivers the lesson. Teachers' teaching technique is effective if it is contextualized based on the learning style of learners. Teaching using traditional methods may not inspire them to participate in learning activities.

More consistently, it was stipulated in the study of Hoelscher (2016) that traditional methods of teaching are good; learners may participate in the discussion, but learning is not too effective to show their academic growth. Mathematics should have a strong foundation to learn for higher level and more complex mathematics skills to strengthen the retention of knowledge since learners may depend on their learning styles and abilities during the learning process (Amalia et al., 2017).

This result further implies that this group of Grade 7 Blaan learners need various teaching strategies to boost their self confidence in learning mathematics.

Post-test Result on Peer Tutoring Method using English-worded Problems in Mathematics Among the Experimental Group of Grade 7 Blaan Learners

A peer tutoring using Blaan-translated word problems was applied to the experimental group of Grade 7 Blaan learners which lasted for four weeks. A 30-item post-test was given to the learners and the results were analyzed. Table 5 shows the result.

Table 5

Post-test Result on Peer Tutoring Method using English-worded Problems in Mathematics Among the Experimental Group of Grade 7 Blaan Learners

Range of Test Scores	f	%	Description
25 – 30	2	6.70%	Very Good
19 – 24	8	26.70%	Good
13 – 18	14	46.60%	Fair
7 – 12	6	20.00%	Poor
0 – 6	0	0.00%	Very Poor
Overall Mean Score		16.60	Fair

The result on Table 5 revealed that 46.60% or most of the learners in the experimental group got scores of 13 to 18 during the post-test on English-worded problems in mathematics. This performance is considered as Fair. Furthermore, 26.7% of the learners who got scores of 19 to 24 are considered to have a Good performance. This is followed by 20% of the learners who scored 7 to 12 having a Poor performance. However, there is 6.70% who got scores of 25-30 which is considered as a Very Good performance, and none of the learners got a score of 0 to 6 which is considered as a Very Poor performance. The mean score of the post-test result among the experimental group on English-worded problems in mathematics is 16.60 which signifies that the learners

perform fairly after the experiment. This shows that there is an improvement in the performance of learners as peer tutoring during the experiment has been employed.

The result shows the effectiveness of peer tutoring during the class discussion. This implies that Blaan learners are more eager to learn if they are assisted by their peers than always listening to their teacher. To teach them with their peers using their own language leads them to learn more and gain better understanding of the discussion. Working with others can help to persuade optimistic peer connections among Blaan learners which in turn can promote desirable behaviour to learn.

In the study of Bosman and Schulze (2018), an application of group or peer learning in class with the assistance of conversant teachers and peers is vital to lessen the learners' experience of difficulties and help them acquire the necessary skills to learn individually. This further emphasizes that learners could not always learn from a teacher but the influence of their peers can also be a prevailing learning resource because learners may be more open to receive the feedback of their peers; the way they communicate with one another is more diverse than when a teacher is in touch with them.

In addition, intervention of peer tutoring using the Blaan language, as applied during the regular class in mathematics, shows a positive effect on both the tutor and the tutees for it helped them increase their ability in understanding the given English-worded problems in mathematics. The development signifies the importance of peer tutoring which shows a positive learning environment where learners are relaxed during the discussion. These improvements were based on the learners' recommendations, as a result of the study conducted by Mazana et al. (2019) which discussed that peer tutoring should be promoted.

Significant Difference on the Result of Post-test Scores Between the Control Group and Experimental Group

This study also assessed whether there is a significant difference between the post-test scores of the control group and experimental group of the Grade 7 Blaan learners. To yield results, t-test for independent samples was employed. Table 6 shows the result.

Table 6

Significant Difference on the Result of Post-test Scores Between the Control Group and Experimental Group

Groups	Mean	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Control	10.77	-4.767	0.000	With Significant Difference
Experimental	16.60			

Mean Difference	5.83			
-----------------	------	--	--	--

Both the control group and experimental group were given a thirty (30) item post-test on English-worded problems in mathematics. The control group got a mean score of 10.77 while the experimental group got a mean score of 16.60. Using the t-test for independent samples, it yields the t-value of -4.767 and the p-value of 0.000. Since $p < 0.05$, then there is Significant Difference in the mean score between the control group and experimental group of Grade 7 Blaan learners in solving English-worded problems in mathematics. This result leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

The result implied that there is a significant difference in learners' interest in learning mathematics between the groups taught using peer tutoring method and traditional lecture-based instruction. The improved learning performance of learners taught with peer tutoring signifies that peer tutoring is effective and could really help slow learners to uplift their performance in their studies especially in mathematics.

Lecture method, as used in the control group, is a traditional way of instruction towards learners which has been used many years back. This method is a teacher-centered learning process. The teacher talks most of the time, which leads to the learners' passiveness in learning. It therefore suggests that educators should constantly aim to use various teaching strategies to improve their learners' knowledge (Retnawati et al., 2017) such as applying peer tutoring among learners during the teaching-learning process. An intervention of peer tutoring among the experimental group forgets the fretful feelings to learn mathematics and instead develop interest to learn more because they are inspired by their peers. Learners who received peer tutoring intervention showed higher interest to learn mathematics than those learners who did not receive the intervention (Fields, 2019). This result showed an optimistic effect on the learners' performance in mathematics, not only to their mastery on the subject but also to their negative emotion toward mathematics turned into positive (Fiers, 2017).

Significant Difference on the Result Between the Pretest and Post-test Among the Control Group

This study evaluated the result of pretest and post-test among the control group of Grade 7 Blaan learners. It aimed whether there is a significant difference in the result of their scores in pretest and post-test. Table 7 shows the result.

Table 7

Significant Difference on the Result Between the Pretest and Post-test Among the Control Group

Category	Mean	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Pretest	9.80	-1.022	0.312	No Significant Difference
Post-test	10.77			
Mean Difference	0.97			

The table revealed the result of the pretest and post-test among the control group of learners. It further shows that the pretest mean score is 9.80 while the post-test mean score is 10.77. As shown in Table 7, the t-value is -1.022 and the p-value is 0.312. Since $p > 0.05$, then there is No Significant Difference in the mean score between the pretest and post-test scores among the control group of Grade 7 Blaan learners in solving English-worded problems in mathematics. This is in line with the recent findings of this study that using a traditional approach has failed to reject the null hypothesis.

The result shows no improvement in the performance of the control group of the Blaan learners. Teaching using a traditional approach leads to an unreceptive attitude of learners. At school, Blaan learners need extraordinary attention that is different from their home. Teachers should be creative in teaching especially in dealing with Blaan learners and avoid teaching using the traditional method approach.

In addition, the traditional method does not provide learners with helpful skills. This method leads to poor retention of knowledge. After the discussion, learners have little or even cannot recall the concept that has been discussed (Tularam, 2018). Learners are made passive and learning interactions are limited only to the teachers and the learners. This teaching did not arouse learners' interest to improve learning and is only appropriate for good communicators (Shivaramaiah, 2018). In addition, in this traditional method of teaching, the connection between the learners and the teacher is far from the learners' expectation. They are afraid to ask questions and are anxious to express their feelings towards the discussion. Teacher-centered approaches in teaching do not consider the individual differences of learners and the teacher's belief is not consistent with how the learners' conviction is being practiced towards learning (Siswono et al., 2019).

Significant Difference on the Result Between the Pretest and Post-test Among the Experimental Group

Finally, this study verified whether there is a significant difference between the pretest and post-test mean scores among the experimental group of Grade 7 Blaan

learners. This further determined whether the performance in solving English-worded mathematical word problems of Grade 7 Blaan learners is affected by the peer tutoring using the Blaan-translated word problems. To find the result, t-test for independent samples was utilized. Table 8 shows the result.

Table 8

Significant Difference on the Result Between the Pretest and Post-test Among the Experimental Group

Category	Mean	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Pretest	9.93	-5.073	0.000	With Significant Difference
Post-test	16.60			
Mean Difference	6.67			

A thirty (30) item pretest and post-test on English-worded mathematical word problems were given among the experimental group of Grade 7 Blaan learners. The table shows that the pretest mean score is 9.93 and the post-test mean score is 16.60. The t-value is -5.073 and the p-value is 0.000. Since $p < 0.05$, then there is a significant difference between the pretest and post-test mean scores among the experimental group of Grade 7 Blaan learners in solving English-worded mathematical word problems.

The result shows that peer tutoring using Blaan-translated word problems significantly affects the performance of Grade 7 Blaan learners in solving English-worded problems in mathematics. This result therefore leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Hence, there is a significant difference between the pretest and post-test performance of the learners among the experimental group. The Blaan learners are well-motivated to learn if they were given the privilege to improve their knowledge using their own language (Perez & Alieto, 2018). Furthermore, an intervention of peer tutoring using Blaan-translated word problems is very influential towards the Blaan learners in learning mathematics. According to Fiers (2017), working with other learners can help to persuade optimistic peer connections which in turn can promote desired behaviours. In addition, the result of this study is similar to the study of Nawaz and Rehman (2017), which showed that peer tutoring brought positive changes in the development of the learners' academic achievement especially in mathematics. In the study of Metila et al. (2016), classrooms utilizing the mother tongue program would often have an option to divert learning into simpler and more comprehensive discussion. This implied a springiness in the policy allowing for practical conclusions to meet the teaching gaps that have been viewed as opportunities to address local needs such as the use of sociocultural language by the learners.

DISCUSSION

Based on the data gathered, the following findings of the study were obtained:

1. Pretest Result on English-worded Problems in Mathematics Among the Control Group of Grade 7 Blaan Learners

The pretest result on English-worded problem in mathematics among the control group based on the perfect score of thirty (30) is Poor as indicated by their mean test score of 9.80.

2. Pretest Result on English-worded Problems in Mathematics Among the Experimental Group of Grade 7 Blaan Learners

The pretest result on English-worded problem in mathematics among the experimental group is Poor based on their mean test score of 9.93.

3. Significant Difference on the Result of Pretest Scores Between the Control Group and Experimental Group of Grade 7 Blaan Learners

As evaluated, the control group and experimental group do not differ on the result of their pretest scores in English-worded problems in the sense that their mean difference is 0.13 with t-value of 1.26 and p-value of 0.900.

4. Post-test Result on English-worded Problems in Mathematics Among the Control Group Among the Grade 7 Blaan Learners

The overall mean score of the control group in their post-test on English-worded mathematical word problems result is 10.77 which revealed that their performance is Poor.

5. Post-test Result on English-worded Problems in Mathematics Among the Experimental Group of Grade 7 Blaan Learners

The post-test result on English-worded mathematical problems among the experimental group is Fair with the over-all mean score of 11.60.

6. Significant Difference on the Result of Post-test Between the Control Group and Experimental Group

T-test for independent sample results (t-value=-4.767, p-value= 0.000) showed that there is a Significant Difference on post-test scores between the control group and experimental group. This revealed that the experimental group of Grade 7 Blaan learners wherein the Blaan-translated word problems were used during the peer tutoring activity,

increased their performance compared to the control group wherein the traditional method of teaching was used.

7. Significant Difference Between the Result of Pretest and Post-test Among the Control Group

The result of the pretest and post-test on English-worded problems in mathematics among the control group with $t\text{-value} = -1.022$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.312$ emphasized that there is No Significant Difference between the two tests.

8. Significant Difference Between the Result of Pretest and Post-test Among the Experimental Group

Finally, the t-test result between the pretest and post-test among the experimental group with the mean difference of 6.67, $t\text{-value} = -5.073$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.000$ showed that the performance of the Grade 7 Blaan learners in solving English-worded problems in mathematics are affected by peer tutoring using Blaan-translated word problems as applied during the regular classes in the experimental group of learners.

The overall result of this study shows that the traditional lecture method is not preferable to be applied among the Blaan learners. They need more creative teaching strategies to motivate them in their studies. Meanwhile, peer tutoring using their mother-tongue language increases the level of performance of the Blaan learners in solving word problems in mathematics. The result shows the positive effect of peer tutoring using Blaan-translated word problems towards the performance of Grade 7 learners. The assistance extended by their peers is valuable and shows commendable performance in learning. Indeed, the findings of this study addressed the gap in the teaching-learning process especially on the difficulties of Blaan learners in their problem solving skills in mathematics.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The level of performance among the control group at the start of the study is Poor.
2. The Poor performance of the experimental group at the start of the study is the same with the control group based on the result of the pretest in solving English-worded problems in mathematics.
3. The control group and experimental group of Grade 7 Blaan learners do not differ in terms of the results on their pretest scores. This means that there is no bias in the subjects utilized in the conduct of the study.
4. The overall mean score of the control group on their post-test revealed that their performance is still Poor when using traditional lecture method on different topics for this study. This emphasizes that using traditional methods in teaching Blaan learners is not effective.

5. Peer tutoring using Blaan-translated word problems in mathematics as employed to the experimental group showed a Fair significant improvement in the Blaan learners' performance based on their post-test result. This reveals that peer tutoring in learning using Blaan language is preferred by the Blaan learners.
6. There is a significant difference in the result of post-test scores between the control group and experimental group.
7. The result of pretest and post-test among the control group emphasized that there is no significant difference between the two tests. Traditional lecture method did not show an improvement to the learners' performance.
8. Finally, the pretest and post-test scores among the experimental group showed that the performance of Grade 7 Blaan learners in solving English-worded problems in mathematics is affected by peer tutoring using Blaan-translated word problems as applied during the regular classes in the experimental group of learners.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Blaan learners may create a buddy system in which knowledgeable learners may assist and motivate their peers who are experiencing difficulties in developing their academic performances to participate actively in various learning activities. Teachers may give rewards to those who have shown an improvement in their academic performance to encourage learners to sustain the system.
2. Mathematics teachers may avoid the traditional lecture method in teaching. Instead, they should be creative and provide effective and sustainable intervention programs across the curriculum learning area to increase the learning skills of Blaan learners such as the application of differentiated instruction.
3. Mathematics and English Coordinators may intensify contextualized reading programs in connection to the subject. Inclusion of mathematical terms during the reading program activity may help Blaan learners in improving their skills in comprehending mathematical terms.
4. The school head may allocate funds for tutorial programs such as materials, venue, and incentives for the tutors and tutees.
5. The parents and tribal community may be called as translators. During the crafting of contextualized worksheets, they may serve as consultants to give accurate translation of the terms to be used in the worksheets.
6. The Department of Education (DepEd) Division Level specifically the Division Mathematics Coordinator may facilitate in crafting a division-wide standardized worksheets such as Blaan-translated word problems in mathematics to be utilized by mathematics teachers in the different schools.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors hereby declare that this research study was conducted in strict compliance with ethical guidelines and standards. Informed consent was obtained from

all subjects prior to their involvement, ensuring that they fully understood the purpose of the study, the nature of their participation, and any potential risks. Learners as subjects were assured of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without any negative consequences or impact on their relationship with the researchers. The anonymity of the respondents was meticulously maintained throughout the research process, and all data collected was kept confidential. The well-being of the subjects was a primary concern, and appropriate measures were taken to safeguard their rights and ensure that their participation posed no harm. Additionally, the authors confirm that there is no conflict of interest in the conduct of this study, and the findings are presented with full integrity. Finally, the research adheres to the highest standards of academic honesty, with strict measures in place to prevent plagiarism, ensuring that all sources are properly cited and acknowledged.

Acknowledgments

Immeasurable appreciation and heartfelt gratitude are extended by the researcher to the people whose time, effort, and support were shared with her for the realization of this research study:

To Dr. Sherwin P. Uy, her thesis adviser and statistician, whose expertise, time and effort guided her throughout the conduct of this research study;

To Dr. Maria Giovanna G. Abecia, the Graduate School Dean and Chair of the panel of experts, with Dr. Lilibeth R. Bagtas and Dr. Tessie R. Colipano, members, for their constructive criticisms, suggestions, and recommendations for the improvement of this research study;

To Mrs. Jenelyn G. Butihen, MT-I, Mrs. Lani L. Paña, MT-I of Tampakan National High School, and Mrs. Susan S. Balaba, MT-I of Liberty National High School, the validators, for their effort and heartfelt support through their time and expertise shared for her study;

To Mr. Jason M. Lantingan of Landan National High School, Mr. Myco I. Ontic of Lusok Integrated School, and Mr. John Enrico C. Peng of Tupi National High School, for validating the compilation of Blaan-Translated word problems as exercises used in peer tutoring during the conduct of her study;

To Nelsie M. Distura, for her expertise in translating the English-worded problems to Blaan;

To the Grade 7 Blaan learners of Lampitak National High School who were the subjects of this study;

To Mrs. Rachel M. Cuevas, for her guidance in accomplishing this study;

To Mr. Noli G. Sebua, her loving husband, Gwyne Zyra Lane G. Sebua her daughter, and Jay Zyrie Luiz G. Sebua her son, who gave their love, inspiration, and hope to pursue this endeavor;

To her brothers and sisters who have extended their support morally and financially;

To her friends and the faculty members of Lampitak National High School for the encouragement and inspiring words towards the completion of this task; and,

To all those who shared and contributed in one way or another in making this research study a successful one.

Most of all the researcher glorifies the Almighty God, who is the source of greatest strength with overflowing blessings. She submits herself and all her life and works, for without His presence and guidance, this research work would not be made possible.

REFERENCES

- Albona, S.M. (2015). Navigating the Learning Labyrinth of B'laan Students: A Phenomenological Study. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research* –March 2015 6(3) Retrieved May 16, 2019, from <https://www.ijser.org/paper/Navigating-the-Learning-Labyrinth-of-Blaan-Students.html>
- Amalia, E., Surya, E. & Syahputra, E. (2017). The Effectiveness of using Problem Based Learning (PBL) in Mathematics Problem Solving Ability for Junior High School Students. *IJARIE*, 4(2).
- Apino, E., & Retnawati, H. (2016). Creative Problem Solving to Improve Students' Higher Order Thinking Skills in Mathematics Instructions. *Proceedings of 3rd International Conference on Research, Implementation and Education of Mathematics and Science*, 339–346. Retrieved from seminar.uny.ac.id
- Department of Education (2015). Adopting the Indigenous Peoples Education Curriculum Framework. Retrieved from <http://www.deped.gov.ph/orders/do-32-s-2015>.
- Eviriyanti, C., Surya, E., Syahputra, E. & Simbolon, M. (2017). Improving the Students' Mathematical Problem Solving Ability by Applying Problem Based Learning Model in VII Grade at SMPN 1 Banda Aceh Indonesia. *International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning*, 4(2), 138–144. Retrieved from noveltyjournals.com
- Fields, J. (2019). The Effects of Peer Mediated Instruction on Students' Knowledge of Basic Math Facts. Theses and Dissertation, Rowan University. Retrieved from rdw.rowan.edu
- Fiers, J. (2017). The Effects of Peer Tutoring on Math Fact Fluency of Elementary Students with Emotional and Behavioral Disorders. *Dissertations and Theses*, Western Illinois University. Retrieved from search.proquest.com
- Garcia, O., & Woodley, H. (2015). Bilingual Education. *The Routledge Handbook of Educational Linguistics*, 132–144. Retrieved from books.google.com
- Hoelscher, L. (2016). Effective strategies for increasing basic math fact fluency. Retrieved from Sophia, the St. Catherine University repository [website:https://sophia.stkate.edu/maed/190](https://sophia.stkate.edu/maed/190)
- Kim, J. (2016). Peer Influence on Children's Reading Skills: A Social Network Analysis of Elementary School Classrooms. *Journal of Education Psychology* [.https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000166](https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000166)
- Mack, N., Woodsong, C., MacQueen, K., & Namey, E. (2005). *Qualitative Research Methods: A Data Collector's Field Guide*. Family Health International.
- McKellar, D. (2006). Danica McKellar's Mathematical Theorem. Retrieved from npr.org
- Mazana, M., Montero, C., Casmir, R. (2019). Investigating Students' Attitude towards Learning Mathematics. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, 14(1), 207–231.
- Metila, R., Pradilla, L., Williams, A. (2016). The challenge of implementing mother tongue education in linguistically diverse contexts: The case of the Philippines. *The Asia-Pacific Education Researcher* 25(5), 781-789.

- Nawaz, A., & Rehman, Z. (2017). Strategy of Peer Tutoring and Students Success in Mathematics: An Analysis. *Journal of Research and Reflections in Education*, 11(1), 15–30.
- Perez, AL. & Alieto, E. (2018). Change of “Tongue” from English to a Local Language: A correlation of Mother Tongue Proficiency and Mathematics Achievement. *The Asian ESP Journal*. 14,132-150.
- Retnawati, H., Kartowagiran, B., Arlinwibowo, J. & Sulistyangsih, E. (2017). Why are Mathematics National Examination Items Difficult and What Is Teachers’ Strategy to Overcome It? *International Journal of Instruction*. 10(3), 257-276.
- Sargeant, J. (2012). Qualitative Research Part II: Participants, Analysis, and Quality Assurance. *Journal of Graduate Medical Education Accreditation Council for Graduate Medical Education*, 4(1), 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.4300>
- Shabani, K., Khatib, M., & Ebadi, S. (2010). Vygotsky’s Zone of Proximal Development: Instructional Implications and Teachers’ Professional Development. *Canadian Center of Science and Education*, 3(4).
- Shivaramaiah, G. (2018). Teaching Learning Methods: Traditional vs Modern vs Peer-Assisted Learning. Xavier University School of Medicine. Retrieved from <https://xusom.com/uncategorized/teaching-learning-methods-traditional-vs-modern-vs-peer-assisted-learning>
- Simamora, R. & Saragih, S. (2019). Improving student’s Mathematical problem Solving Ability and Efficacy through Guided Discovery Learning in Local Culture Contest. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*. 14(1); 61-72.
- Simamora, R., Sidabutar, D., & Surya, E. (2017). Improving Learning Activity and Students’ Problem Solving Skill Through Problem Based Learning (PBL) in Junior High School. *International Journal of Sciences: Basic and Applied Research (IJSBAR)*, 33(2), 321–331. Retrieved from [researchgate.net](https://www.researchgate.net)
- Siswono, TY, Juniati, D. & Muhtarom, H. (2019). Examining Prospective Teachers’ Belief and Pedagogical Content Knowledge Towards Teaching Practice in Mathematics Class: A Case Study. *Journal of Mathematics Education*, 10(2), 185-202.
- Tiburcio, C., Quines, L., & Guhao, E. (2018). The Meaning of Project-Based Learning among B’laan High School Students: A Phenomenological Study. *International Journal of Management Excellence*, 11(2).
- Tularam, G. (2018). Traditional vs Non-Traditional Teaching and Learning Strategies-the case of E-learning. *International Journal for Mathematics Teaching and Learning*, 19(1)
- Vygotsky, L.S. (1987). *Thinking and Speech*. Plenum Press, New York.
- Zakaria, E., & Syamaun, M. (2017). The Effect of Realistic Mathematics Education Approach on Students’ Achievement and Attitudes towards Mathematics. *Mathematics Education Trends and Research 2017*, 34–40.